

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY THROUGH WEBSITE CONTENT AS MARKETING COMMUNICATION STRATEGY OF HALAL FASHION

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Abstract: Indonesia, as a biggest population country in the world should notice the halal product consumed in daily life. Halal term refers to some indicator, raw material, supply chain management until marketing process. The implementation of digital technology in marketing process is expected to increase brand awareness and profit the fashion halal. The research subject is the first world halal socks company website as media promotion and information to accelerate the brand awareness as halal socks. The approach used in this research is qualitative method. It is in-depth interview and observation through the website. The process of data collection is conducted through interviews, observations of website design. The result of the study is increasing the brand awareness by using website technology consists of two pages including admin page content and main page content which can provide the information and friendly user system of halal fashion product to provide up to date online information the brand awareness of consumer. The use of website as a marketing and promotion medium is to provide up to date online information to become an alternative promotional of brand as part of marketing communication activity, which has a wider reach and it is expected to expand market share and brand awareness.

Keywords: brand awareness, halal fashion, information technology, website

I. Introduction

Indonesia is the largest Muslim country in the world where around 80% of the population should obey Islamic Law more deeply, including the used of halal products in the daily life of a Muslim. Halal products are made from raw materials, manufacturing process (tools, machines, production stages) that zero-contained haram or subhat elements, also received halal certification from the official Halal Institution.

During 2020 – 2030, Indonesia will experience a demographic bonus. The number of young people will penetrate 40% of the total population of Indonesia. (Faizal, 2017). Indonesia faces millennial generation era which is the first generation to bear digital native that using of information technology as the primary sources' interaction.

Based on the research "Platform halal lifestyle using one stop solution application" by Ativa Hesti A, Risky Dwi Afriadi, Ceasar Pratama & Ade Lestari showed there were many things that can be done to provide opportunities in the current era of globalization has a significant and positive impact on number of business to produce and market halal lifestyle goods and services for a wider scale and market. The presence of information technology has created many business opportunities to introduce halal lifestyle. The internet is the significant instrument to process the transforming business towards digitalization. This condition allows cost-efficient for interaction,

transformation and increasing the revenue of product. The recent study by Simanjuntak, Risa confirmed the online experience has become an integral part of younger generations to date. The amount of time used online documented the activities and opinions of these young people as well as the interactions amongst them.

This research objective is to analyze the website content as part of digital transformation on halal socks business. Website is able to provide information to be more efficient and up to date. The website is more easily accessible to people in various region by simply using the internet. For example, website can be used for media information, communication, promotion and marketing. Website is very suitable media to introduce the product to various potential market and wider community.

II. Literature Review

Information is data that has been classified, processed or interpreted for use in the decision making process. The information processing system will process data into information or process data from meaningless form to be meaningful for those who receive it.

According to Wahyu Eko Susanto (2015) the Web is an application that contains multimedia documents includes text, images, sound, animation and video that uses a protocol HTTP (hypertext transfer protocol) and to access using software called browser. The website functions include as media promotion, media marketing, media information, media education and media communication.

Further more, the statement from Anhar (2010, 23) hypertext pre-processor is a web programming language in the form of scripts that can be integrated with HTML (Hypertext mark-up language) as the standard mark up language for documents designed to be displayed in a web browser

Previous study from Gunawan, Wahyu stated the using of MySQL (my structure query language) as an application or system for managing databases or data management. To store all information on the computer using data. MySQL is in charge of managing data in the database, besides MySQL is known as an efficient and reliable system, the query process is fast and easy, making suitable for use on web -based applications.

Promotion comes from the word promote in English which is defined as develop or improve. Promotion is one component of the marketing mix. Promotion also interpreted as an effort to notify or offer product and service in order to persuade potential customer to buy.

Website

Information on the web generally categorized into three types according to Rusdianto (014:76-77),namely: 1. General Information that consisting of general service information or online news, 2. Information that is special web with information content about an institution or company. 3. Information of a Commercial nature which is Information that is beneficial for sale value. As a medium of communication, the company's official website has several advantages: 1. Companies can use the main website address as desired and more specific so that it easier to be searched through search engines. 2. Information that is published only about the company website, so that the information conveyed is more focused. 3.The company can modify the appearance and facilities on its official website as needed 4. The company is fully responsible for the design and content of its official website. 5. Potential of the website can be utilized to increase understanding of the company activities.

The website application has characteristics, which can be described as follows:

- a. Web application tend to continue to increase , in the sense of the word that new website application development will be realized when the application is implemented
- b. The content consists of various forms and data format such as text, graphics, image, audio, video which are integrated by procedural processing (web programming) the methods used in displaying and managing the content will have an impact on the response time in the system

- c. The website application is intended for use by a large, diverse user community and a number of unknown users (public users) with various needs, expectations and abilities. Therefore, the development of website applications user interfaces and usability features are expected to be able to answer the needs of all these users without having to go through a training program
- d. The web application demands a good look and feel aspects, which is an aspect that meets aesthetic and artistic values, so that users feel comfortable using and accessing the developed website application.
- e. Rapid technological changes pose challenges for website technology and standards such as the development of new languages, new tools and new standards which may have errors and bugs
- f. Content delivery medium for website applicants is very different from traditional software. Web applications require compatibility with various types of display devices, display formats, hardware and software support
- g. Security and privacy are more required by web-based systems when compared to traditional software

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Applications in Marketing Strategy

One of the applications from Information and Communication Technology (ICT)) and the Internet in Business and Commerce is electronic commerce (e-commerce). E-commerce can be define as the e-business application related to commercial transactions, such as: transfer of electronic funds, supply chain management (SCM), e-Marketing (e-marketing) or online marketing, online transaction processing, electronic data interchange (EDI), product promotion, etc.

The business and trade sectors are strongly influenced by the development of Information technology, especially in the use of internet. (Jauhari, 2010). The marketing and sales activities can be carried out any time without being bound by space and time (Quaddus and Xu, Jinling et al, 2009). The ability of the internet to transmit various forms of data such as text graphics, images, sound, animation and video pursue business are taking advantage of this technology by creating a homepage to promote their business. Marketing with conventional method requires high costs for opening new branches, participating in exhibitions, making and distributing brochures, etc. The development of Internet has become an efficient medium of opening new marketing channels. Besides the low cost, utilizing the Internet, information dissemination will be faster and wider in reach.

The benefits and advantages using e-commerce are promotional media in order to increase sales volume, both for online and conventional sales. Apart from these advantages, the results of several studies show that the effectiveness of using e-commerce in boosting sales volume and promotional industrial products.

III Research Methods

The approach used in this research is qualitative method. It is in-depth interview, case-oriented study to make a fact understandable and does not emphasize the predictions of various patterns found. It is conducted in a descriptive manner as scientific observation to explain a certain condition and eliminate judgement that arise because of impressions. The design describes any data which is saved to database and explain the relationship between the data as overall.

IV. Findings

System Implementation includes interface design data structures in the form of data base tables, creating program code.

Front Displays

The home page, it is created to for to disseminate information products that are produced by the company and facilitate online sales transaction. It requires website developers and users, among others: webmaster (admin) is someone who can process and design the website interface and develop the website. User, namely all people who can enter to view the website and have the right to access the website by registering to become a. member. Users do not have the right to manage or control the website as a whole.

Login ×

Email

Password

[Lupa Password](#)

LOGIN

Belum punya akun? [Daftar Sekarang](#)

The front display has customer page as a public page that can be accessed by website visitors who want to view and buy the products. There is customer page features to view products, place order for products. On this page, the customer must register before ordering a product, otherwise customer are not to be able to carry out the purchasing process

Slide Form

1

2

Category Form Displays

It is kind of content navigation interactivity. The aims of this tools to increase the usability e-commerce website to offer an efficient navigation in order to achieve the user pleasure. The result is more successful interaction and may help the user to make a purchase

Order Form Displays

Customers who want to purchase products do not have to log in first. Customers can immediately carry out the purchase process by selecting a product. Products that have been selected will be entered into a shopping bag. The customer carries out a checking process to find out whether the product in the shopping bag is available. If the product ordered is suitable, the customer can proceed with the check out process and then fill in all the procedures including customer data, shipping method, payment method and making order confirmation.

Product Form Displays

The product category display contains the type of product as well as the appearance of the product and the selling price of the product. The contents is in clear way to making ease the search of information. It is organized by provide quality information and visualization with proper size

Contact Form Displays

The contact form is easy to find and has link to active social media accounts such as Twitter, Instagram and Facebook. It gives customer a way to engage with the company and describe how the company can help solve the customer problems and become their solutions.

V. Conclusion

Website design as a medium promotions and information of fashion halal divide to admin pages (including category, product, login, slide) that are managed by admin, while the main website pages such as order and contact forms can be managed by the customers. Website as promotional and information media has content function such as publish news, product, activities and promotion. The interaction with the customers can be managed online direct through website without requiring consumers to come directly to offline shop. The use of website as a marketing and promotion medium is expected to provide up to date information online to become an alternative promotional of brand as part of marketing communication activity, which has a wider reach and it is expected to expand market share and brand awareness.

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